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Influence of Digital Technology on Organisational Communication in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of digital technology on organisational communication in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo. The objectives of the study include to find out if Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo uses digital technologies in their communication; identify the digital technologies used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo; determine the extent of usage of digital technologies by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo; examine the influence of digital technologies on organisational communication practice in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo; and identify the challenges that Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo faces in its use of digital technology. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, with a questionnaire used as an instrument for gathering data. The population of the study comprised staff of Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, which, according to the Human Resources Unit, is 600. The study, which was anchored on the technological determinism theory and the technological acceptance theory, revealed that 85% of respondents agreed that the organisation uses digital technologies in its communication. Furthermore, 50% of the respondents agreed that the predominant technology used in Champion Breweries Plc was photos, slides, digital photography, laptops, computers, and iPads. The study further revealed that the majority of respondents (74%) were of the opinion that the use of digital technology has influenced organisational communication. It was recommended that awareness and adoption of

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new technologies by employees should be encouraged through training and retraining exercises by ICT experts through seminars, conferences, workshops, and organisations, and institutions should embrace new technologies in their communication strategies in order to improve their organisation's communication practice.

Keywords: Influence, Digital Technology, Organisations, Organisational Communication, and Champion breweries.

Introduction

Communication remains an indisplaceable necessity for corporate and human sustainability (Udokop et al., 2023). The word “communication” is derived from the Latin word “communis,” which means “common” (Nwanne, 2012, p. 238–239). Communication is one of the most important activities in any organisation (Akarika et al., 2022). Akarika (2021, p. 67) defines communication as “an expression of thoughts, feelings, ideas, and messages from the sender to the receiver through verbal, non-verbal, written, and non-written forms.” Baran (2007, p. 4) added that communication is “the transmission of a message from a source to a receiver. This means that for communication to be effective, the encoder and the receiver should be able to express their ideas. Communication is one of the most dominant and important functions in an organisation (Harries & Nelson, 2018). Communication is essential for the internal function of the organisation because it integrates the management function (Akarika, 2020). The major objectives of communication in any organisation are to inform and educate employees at all levels on the “... strategy and motivate them to support the strategy and organisational performance goals (Akarika et al., 2022).

Communication has a vital role in an organisation's life. It is one of the main things that must be owned in order to achieve organisational goals and objectives (Akarika et al., 2021). According to Akarika (2020), communication flow is essential for an organisation that desires to improve its performance. The advent of digital technologies has had a profound impact on the practice of communication in today's society. This shift in the media world, which is mostly based on the usage of digital computers, such as the internet, and other portable digital devices such as cell phones, iPods, and MP3 players, to name a few, is significant (Akpan et al., 2022). The new media are diverse groups of communication technologies that share some traits apart

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from being new, made feasible by digitalization, and widely available for personal use as communication devices (McQuail, 2005).

Despite the roles the new media technologies play, several obstacles still stand in their way to effective and efficient usage, particularly in Nigeria. Gbam (2017), cited in Akpan et al. (2020), identified the challenges to include: no clear-cut policies, cost of acquisition of new media technologies, low level of technical penetration, power supply, and lack of expertise. Others include the cost of ICT facilities, a lack of adequate infrastructure, and the challenge of sustainability (Igyuve, Inobemhe, Udeh, & Ugber, 2020). To further buttress this point, Danaan (2006) argues that constant electric power outages in Least Developed Countries (LDC), of which Nigeria is one, pose a serious threat to the internal survival of ICTS.

Digital technology and its increasing prevalence have impacted human life radically in the last few decades. From the advent of the digital society, spawned by the invention of the computer and the ENIAC (Electronic Numerical Integrated Arithmetic Computer), one of the first digital computers in 1946 (Wikipedia), to the present day, digital technology and computing have worked their way into more areas of life, from communications to finance to social interaction.

According to Bonin (2013, p. 1), we now “experience... through the eyes of technology,” noting that digital media are the new means through which... products are felt. “Unlike earlier technologies, these enable online communities built by readers, listeners, and viewers to discuss topics, have their views heard, and receive responses in record time.” (Bonin, 2013, p. 1). The new digital technology, according to O'Sullivan and Heinonen (2008), provides a fresh platform for addressing people. It has become ingrained in news collection and processing routines, raising a slew of new challenges regarding methods.

The advent of digital technology is a result of developments in the way organisations communicate. It is changing the entire landscape of organisational communication. Memos, emails, newsletters, and campaign reports are beginning to be threatened by the immediacy and other interactive features brought about by the new media (Akarika et al., 2022). New media and digital technologies are having a major impact on how organisations consume information or messages. People can now communicate with each other through email, social media, chat messages, video conferencing, video cables, phones, videos, symbols, graphs, charts, and emotions, among other things. (Ntuk et al., 2022).

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Statement of the Problem

Champion Breweries Plc is a Nigerian brewing company located in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Champion Breweries Plc is operating in a highly competitive Nigerian beer market, and to remain competitive, the company needs to focus on quality and efficiency in its operations. The company has adopted communication principles and effective communication practices to improve its operations. However, it is not clear whether these initiatives have had a significant impact on the company's performance since the advent of digital technology.

However, there is a lack of empirical research on the influence of digital technology on organisational communication in Champion Breweries Plc, specifically. It is not clear whether the company's adoption of digital technology in organisational communication practices has led to improvements in its operations or whether there are other factors that may be hindering the company's performance. Hence, the importance of answering this question: what is the influence of digital technology on organisational communication practices on the operations of Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

- i. Find out if Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo use digital technologies in their communication.
- ii. Identify the digital technologies used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo.
- iii. Determine the extent of digital technology usage by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo.
- iv. Examine the influence of digital technologies on organisational communication practices in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo.
- v. Identify the challenges that Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo faces in their use of digital technology.

Research Questions

- i. Do Champion Breweries Plc Uyo use digital technologies in their communication?
- ii. What are the digital technologies used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, in their organisational communication?

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- iii. To what extent has Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo utilised digital technology in their organisational communication?
- iv. Has the use of digital technology influenced organisational communication practices in Champion Breweries Plc Uyo?
- v. What are the challenges faced by Champion Breweries Plc in their use of digital technology?

Literature Review

Concepts of Communication

Communication is a fundamental aspect of human interaction that plays a critical role in various areas of life, including the business world (Ongori & Migiro, 2010). In the business world, effective communication is crucial for building strong relationships with clients, customers, and stakeholders. Aref (2021) explains that communication in the business world takes different forms, including verbal and written communication, digital communication, and nonverbal communication. Communication is the act of conveying information from one person or group of people to another (Robbins et al., 2017). Effective communication involves the exchange of information, ideas, and opinions in a clear, concise, and timely manner. It is an essential element in any organisation, as it enables people to work together towards a common goal. According to a study by the Harvard Business Review, communication is one of the top three skills that employers look for in employees (Amabile & Kramer, 2011).

Effective communication helps to ensure that everyone in the organisation is on the same page, with a shared understanding of the company's goals, objectives, and strategies (Smith, 2019). According to Smith (2019), this can help to improve coordination, reduce errors, and enhance productivity. Effective communication can also help to build trust and strong relationships with clients, customers, and stakeholders. By listening to feedback and addressing concerns promptly, businesses can build a loyal customer base and improve their brand reputation.

In the last decade, communication has become even more important due to the rise of remote work and virtual teams. With the advancement of technology, employees can now work from anywhere in the world, and communication has become even more critical for the success of a business. Effective communication can help to improve collaboration, coordination, and productivity, leading to improved organisational

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performance (Gibson & Hodgetts, 2019). According to Alfandi (2020), effective communication is essential for organisational success. Communication is the exchange of information between individuals or groups in an organization. Effective communication can help to improve employee morale, reduce conflicts, and enhance organisational performance.

The success of any organisation depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of its communication system and the nature of its independent relationships. (Akarika et al., 2021). According to Akarika et al. (2021, p. 116), "failure to communicate with employees leads to misunderstandings, false rumours, and confusion, as it is in any organization." Therefore, a two-way channel of communication is essential to give workers an opportunity to ask questions about the organisation or to make suggestions to the management.

Concepts of Organisational Communication

The concept of organisational communication has been considered an important and challenging area that strengthens the connection between an organisation and its stakeholders, in particular employees, as it bridges the gap between them and the management. Grunig and Dozier (2002) argue that one way to achieve the connection between managers and employees is through effective organisational communication, which becomes a catalyst for organisations to reach their goals and objectives, as effective organisational communication enables them to effectively develop structure and culture. Organisational communication is listed among the 60 factors affecting organisational effectiveness (Welch, 2008).

According to Hayase (2009), the approach to organisational communication has had to adjust and adapt to the numerous changes taken from the literature. It is evident that there are numerous definitions provided by different authors in the field of internal communication. According to Forssberg and Halm (2001), scholars in the field of organisational communication further define it in terms of the perceived functions, goals, and expectations, as well as its context, that is, the roles organisational communication is expected to fulfil.

Erlie (2003) assesses organisational communication as the flow of information and exchange of ideas and opinions between managers and co-workers, as well as the communication between individuals and groups at different levels and in different units

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or parts of an organisation. In their definition, Welch and Jackson (2007) define organisational communication as “a process between an organisation's strategic managers and its internal stakeholders, designed to promote commitment to an organisation, a sense of belonging to it, awareness of its changing environment, and understanding evolving aims.”.

Concepts of Digital Technology

The use of digital technology in communication practice has become increasingly popular in recent years. Digital technology has provided individuals and organisations with new tools and channels to engage with audiences and measure the impact of their communication efforts (Berkowin, 2016). One of the major ways digital technologies has influenced communication practices in institutions is the emergence of social media platforms. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram have become popular means of communication. Iroha (2019) notes that in practice, social media is the front-runner tool used by top organisations and big institutions for brand awareness, audience prospecting, and relationship building.

Through social media, organisations connect with their target audiences, engage with them, and communicate relevant information. This has made it easier for organisations to promote their brand, showcase their achievements, and address concerns from the public. Yang (2020) notes that social media platforms have become a popular means of communication, enabling organisations to connect with their publics, promote their institution's brand, and address concerns from the public. Aside from being able to enhance communication flow, digital technology has also made it easier for organisations to monitor their brand reputation.

Digital technology has also influenced communication practices in organisations through the use of digital media. Organisations can use digital media such as videos, infographics, and podcasts to communicate information to their target audience. Research has shown that the use of digital media in communication can improve engagement and recall among the audience (Huang & Lin, 2019). This has made it easier for organisations to communicate complex information in a simple and engaging manner. Digital media can be shared on social media platforms, institution websites, and other digital channels, making it easier for organisations to reach their target audience. Digital media such as videos, infographics, and podcasts have become

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popular means of communication, enabling organisations to communicate complex information in a simple and engaging manner (Huang & Lin, 2019).

Types of Digital Technology

Websites

Websites are one of the most popular methods for individuals to access the web, which is a result of several pieces of digital technology. A well-maintained and attractive company website can offset potential negative online publicity from unhappy customers or former employees. The organisation may use the company website to communicate with the public, consumers, and members of other media outlets (Frenz, 2007; cited in Udomah et al., 2023).

Internet

The Internet is a system architecture that has revolutionised communication and commerce by allowing various computer networks around the world to interconnect (Kahn et al., 2023).

Smart phones

A smartphone is a cellular telephone with an integrated computer and other features not originally associated with telephones, such as an operating system (OS), web browsing, and the ability to run software. Smartphones are used by consumers and as part of a person's business or work (<https://www.techtarget.com>).

Video Streaming

Video streaming is the continuous transmission of video files from a server to a client. Video streaming enables users to view videos online without having to download them. Streamed video content can include movies, TV shows, YouTube videos, and livestreamed content (<https://www.techtarget.com>).

Tablet computers

A tablet computer is a wireless, portable personal computer with a touchscreen interface. The tablet form factor is typically smaller than a notebook computer but larger than a smartphone. The idea of tablet computing is generally credited to Alan Kay of

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Xerox, who sketched out the idea in 1971 (<https://www.techtarget.com>).

According to Paul et al. (2022), other examples of digital technology include:

Digital Television

Digital technology has transformed televisions in numerous ways. For starters, both the picture and audio quality have undergone dramatic improvements. Modern televisions can also be used to stream movies and shows, rather than just receive programmes via an antenna or cable connection.

E-Books

Digital alternatives to traditional print are now plentiful. This enables users to access a multitude of reading materials from a single, portable device, so there's no longer the need to carry around a lot of bulky, heavy books. It's easy to alter the font size and style to suit reader preferences. Unlike with print books, there are no trees cut down to make them.

Blogs

Digital technology has enabled the creation of blogs, which are now commonly found across the web. These regularly updated websites usually contain personal reflections, typically written in an informal style. They are also increasingly interactive, containing links to videos and other media, and are often accompanied by readers' comments.

Social Media

Social media sites, such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, have seen an explosion in popularity in recent years. They bring together multiple pieces of digital technology to enable users to interact via text, photos, and video, as well as form social groups. Social media applications rely almost entirely on user-generated content. Today's slim tablets and laptops are nothing like the original computers, which were enormous and stationary.

Printers

A printer is another digital device that is so commonplace nowadays that we pretty much take it for granted. Although in recent years, information has increasingly tended to be

stored rather than printed, life without these output devices would still be difficult to imagine. We also should not forget 3D printers, which are increasingly presenting both new opportunities and challenges.

Digital Cameras

These devices have much greater versatility than traditional cameras, especially when used in conjunction with other digital technology. Digital images are easier to store, organise, edit, email, and print. Most digital cameras can also capture video.

Challenges of using Digital Technologies for Organisational Communication

Organisations and institutions face several challenges when using digital technology tools. Keeping up with the changing digital trends, technology, or tools that are continuously evolving can be problematic. According to Huang & Lin (2019), these changes can be a challenge for organisations, as they need to stay up-to-date with the latest platforms, tools, and strategies to effectively communicate with their audience. Some of these challenges include the following:

1. The challenges of managing online reputation: With the widespread use of social media and other digital platforms, it can be challenging to maintain the reputation of an organisation online. Organisations need to monitor and respond to feedback, comments, and reviews in a timely and appropriate manner.
2. The challenge of ensuring message consistency: With the increasing number of digital channels, it can be difficult to maintain consistency in messaging across all platforms. Organisations need to ensure that the messaging is consistent, accurate, and aligned with the institution's values and goals.
3. The challenges of managing data privacy and security: Organisations need to ensure that they are compliant with data privacy and security laws when collecting and using data from digital channels. They need to take appropriate measures to protect the personal information of their audience and ensure that the institution's digital channels are secure.
4. The challenge of measuring effectiveness: Organisations need to be able to measure the effectiveness of their digital campaigns and strategies to determine

their impact and organisation. They need to have access to relevant metrics and data to track performance and adjust their strategies accordingly.

5. Handling negative feedback: With the ease of communication on digital platforms, negative feedback and criticism can spread quickly. Organisations need to have a plan in place to handle negative feedback and respond in a way that addresses the issue and maintains the institution's reputation.
6. The challenge of overcoming information overload: With the abundance of information available on digital platforms, it can be overwhelming for the audience to process all the information. Organisations need to ensure that the information they provide is relevant and easily digestible, so that it is not ignored or overlooked.
7. The challenge of building engagement: Engaging with the audience on digital platforms can be a challenge, especially with the increasing competition for attention. PROs need to find creative ways to engage with their audience and keep them interested and involved. With the increasing number of digital platforms available, organisations need to manage multiple platforms simultaneously. This can be time-consuming and requires additional resources. Hence, adapting to new technologies is constantly emerging, and organisations need to stay on top of these developments to leverage them for effective communication. However, adopting new technologies can also be challenging, as it may require additional training and investment.

Theoretical Framework

This study relied on the following theories:

Technological Determinism theory and Technological Acceptance theory.

Technological Determinism Theory

The Technological Determinism Theory was proposed by Everret Rogers in 1986. The term was coined by an American sociologist and economist, Thorstein Veblen (1851–1929). The theory revolves around the proposition that technology in any given

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society defines its nature. Technology is viewed as the driving force of culture in a society, and it determines its course in history.

Technological determinism is a reductionist theory that aims to provide a causative link between technology and a society's nature. It tries to explain to whom or what could have a controlling power in human affairs. The theory questions the degree to which human thought or action is influenced by technological factors. The theory assumes that a society's technology determines the development of its social and cultural values.

Karl Marx provided an elaboration of a technological determinist view of socio-economic development, whose theoretical framework was grounded in the perspective that changes in technology, and specifically, productive technology, have the primary influence on human social relations and organisational structure, and that social relations and cultural practices ultimately revolve around the technological and economic base of a given society. The technological determinist view is a technology-led theory of social change. Technology is seen as the prime mover in history.

This theory is relevant to the present study because technology is seen as a prime mover, so organisations will not want to be left behind.

Technological Acceptance Theory

Technological acceptance theory was introduced by Fred Davis in 1986. The theory postulates that the use of an information system is determined by behavioural intention, and behavioural intention is determined by the person's attitude towards the use of a system and by his perception of its utility. According to Davis, the attitude of an individual is not the only factor that determines his use of a system; it is also based on the impact it may have on its performance. This means the probability that an individual will use a certain technology is high if he or she perceives that the system will improve his or her performance at work.

According to Davis, perceived usefulness (PU) is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system is free of physical and mental effort. Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness positively affect the individual's attitudes towards an information system and also positively affect the individual's intentions to use and accept the information system. Scholars have already confirmed that PU has a positive relationship with both adoption and intention (Bryon & Schoster,

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2005). The theory focuses on the adoption and use of information and communication technology (ICT). It explains the determinants of user acceptance of a wide range of end-user computing technologies (Oguoshi, 2020). This theory is relevant to the present study in that organisations are trying to integrate digital technologies into their communication practices because of their perceived usefulness and perceived cases of use to enhance their performance.

Research Methodology

The study made use of a survey research design, with a questionnaire used as an instrument to gather data. Survey is a research method used to gather information on the beliefs, attitudes, opinions, and views of people about various issues and events in society (Berger, 2000; Gunter, 2000; Rubin, 2008; Rubbin et al., 2010; Wimmer & Dominick, 2011). The population of the study comprised staff of Champion Breweries Plc Uyo, which according to the Human Resources Unit is 600. The sample size for the study was determined at 278 using Philip Mayer's (1979) sampling size determination table.

Table i: Table for Determining sample size from a given Population

Population	Sample size
1,000,000-above	384
500,000	381
100,000	383
50,000	381
10,000	370
5,000	357
3,000	341
2,000	322
1,000	278

Source: Krejcie and Morgan (1970): Educational and Psychological Measurement.

The multiple sampling technique was used. The cluster sampling technique was used at the first stage to divide champion breweries into clusters according to departments, while the available sampling technique was used at the last stage to select

respondents for the study. Out of 278 copies of the questionnaire administered to respondents, 270 were returned and found usable for the study. Thus, representing a return rate of 97% and a mortality rate of 3%. The data gathered from the study was analysed using simple percentages and distribution tables.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Response on if Champion Breweries Plc Uyo use Digital technologies in their communication

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	230	85
No	30	11
Undecided	10	4
Total	270	100

Table 1 show that Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo use one form of digital media or the other in their communication at attested to by 85% of respondents.

Table 2: Extent of utilization of digital technology in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo

Option	Frequency	Percentage
A very great extent	60	22
A great extent	60	22
Undecided/neutral	-	-
A little extent	50	19
A very little extent	100	37
Total	270	100

Table 2 shows that majority of respondents (100) representing 37% agreed that the extent of usage of digital technologies is a very little extent. This implies that the extent of usage of digital technologies is minimal.

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Table 3: Respondents opinion on the influence of digital technology on organisational communication in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo

Option	Frequency	Parentage
Yes	200	74
No	70	26
Total	270	100

Table 3 shows that majority of respondents (74%) were of the opinion that the use of digital technology by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, has an influence on its organisational communication.

Table 4: Predominant digital technology used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo in their organisational communication practice

Option	No of Respondents	Percentage
Television/video/white boards	20	7
Audio tape, record player/DVD	40	15
Photos/slide/digital photography/websites	60	22
Laptops/computers/ipads/internet	75	28
e-mail	40	15
Social media	25	9
Vlos/Podcast	5	2
Others, please specify	-	-
All of the above	5	2
Total	270	100

Table 4 shows that the majority of the respondents (60, 75) representing 22% and 28%, respectively, said that the predominant digital technology used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo were photos, slide, digital photography, laptops, computers and Ipods, internet, websites.

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Table 5: Challenges faced by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo in the usage of digital technology in their organisational communication

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Insufficient resources	7	12
Inadequate access to technology	3	5
Lack of organisational support by management	11	19
Perceptions about the use of technology and its impact on culture.	5	8.5
Lack of knowledge and expertise by employees on the use of digital technology		
Focus on using technology for computer-based testing of products rather than communication	5	8.5
Negative attitude of employee about technology	3	5
All of the above	25	42
Total	270	100

Table 5 captures the Challenges faced by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo in the use of digital technologies in communication. The majority of respondents (42%) were of the opinion that the following barriers were impediments to full integration of digital technologies: insufficient resources, inadequate access to technology, lack of financial support by management, negative perception about the use of technology and its impact on culture, lack of knowledge and expertise on the part of employees, focus on using technology for computer-based testing rather than communication and negative attitude of employees about technology.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study are therefore discussed in line with the research questions:

Research Question 1: Does Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, use digital media technologies in its organisational communication?

The data gathered and presented in table 1 show that the majority of respondents (230), representing 85%, agreed that they used digital technologies in the organisation. The findings of this study give credence to Berkowitz (2016), who observed that the use of digital technology in communication practice has become increasingly popular in recent years and has provided new tools and channels to engage with their publics and measure the impact of their communication efforts. Findings further agree with Yang (2020), who noted that social media platforms have become popular means of communication, enabling organisations to engage with their publics, promote their brand, and address communication.

Research Question 2: What are the digital technologies used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, in organisational communication?

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents (85%) agreed that Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, uses digital technology in their communication.

Table 4 captures vividly the predominant digital technologies used by Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo. The majority of respondents, 135 (50%), said that they used photos, slides, digital photography, laptops, computers, and iPods. This implies that the listed items were integrated into communication practices by the management of Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo. The findings of this study give credence to the types of digital technology, which include smartphones, tablet computers, digital telecom, digital routers, the internet, websites, and others.

Findings of this study corroborate the assertion that recently, different forms of digital media, such as photos, slide shows, iPods, and laptops, were being used by organisations.

Research Question 3: To what extent has Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, utilised digital technology in their organisational communication?

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents (37%) were of the opinion that

the extent to which the integration of digital technologies was used was very little. This implies that the extent of utilisation of digital technologies was minimal. The findings of the study negate the various research studies on the popularity of digital technology. According to Huang and Lin (2019), digital media have become a popular means of communication, enabling organisations to communicate complex information in a single and engaging manner. Findings also negate the outcome of research that shows that the use of digital media in communication can improve engagement and recall among the audience (Huang & Lin 2019).

Research question 4: Has the use of digital technology influenced organisational communication practices in Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo?

The data gathered and presented in table 3 captures the opinions of respondents on the influence of digital technology on organisational communication in Champion Breweries plc, Uyo.

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents, 200 (74%), were of the opinion that the use of digital technology by champion Breweries Plc, Uyo, has influenced organisational communication practice. The findings of this study corroborate Akpan et al. (2022), who observed that the advent of digital technology has a profound impact on the practice of communication. This shift in the media world, which is mostly based on the usage of digital computers such as the internet, cell phones, iPods, and MP3 players, is significant. Similarly, the advent of digital technology is changing the entire landscape of organisational communication. Memos, emails, newsletters, and campaign reports are beginning to be threatened by interactive features brought about by the new media (Akarika et al., 2022).

Research Question 5: What are the challenges that Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo faces in their use of digital communication?

Table 5 captures their challenges. The majority of respondents (42%) were of the opinion that the following were challenges faced by Champion Breweries plc, Uyo in the usage of digital technology: insufficient resources, inadequate access to technology, lack of support by organisations, negative perceptions of the use of technology and its impact on culture, lack of knowledge and expertise on the part of employees, a focus on using technology for computer-based testing rather than communication, and a negative

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attitude of employees about technology. Findings of this study agree with those of the study by Gbam (2017), cited in Akpan et al. (2020), who identified the challenges as including lack of clear policies, high cost of acquisition, low level of technical operation, low power supply, and lack of expertise. Others include the high cost of ICT facilities, a lack of infrastructure, and challenges of sustainability (Igyure et al. 2020).

Conclusion

Digital technology has had a profound impact on communication practices in Champion Breweries Plc. It has enabled Champion Breweries Plc to connect with their public, monitor their brand reputation, deliver targeted messages, facilitate two-way communication, and measure the impact of their communication efforts. With the popularity of digital technologies, organisations cannot afford to be apathetic to the use of digital technology in communication. They must also be aware of the challenges that come with the rise of digital technology and be prepared to adapt to the evolving landscape of organisational communication practice. Champion Breweries Plc, as an organisation, must be vigilant and critical in their assessment of each digital tool to ensure credibility and accuracy of information when communicating with the public.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. Awareness and adoption of new technologies by Champion Breweries Plc employees should be encouraged by management through training and retraining exercises carried out by ICT experts through seminars, conferences, and workshops.
2. Champion Breweries Plc, Uyo should embrace new technologies in their communication in order to improve their organisation's communication practices.

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